

Feedback overview of Piloted Modules

“Project management for EU urban
transformation in the context of climate
change and energy transition”

101126659-PM4U-ERASMUS-JMO-2023-HEI-TCH-RSCH

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1. Module description

Piloted module was provided within the course I-RP-E-UI “Territorial and Project Management” from 11 to 15 of March, 2024. The format of the module was provided as intensive block-week that included 40 hours. The theme of the block week reflected current problems in the field of project and territory management. During the block week, both theoretical developments and their application in practice were considered.

Teachers:

Prof. Oleksii Yehorchenkov, M.Sc., PhD, Dr.Sc, Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava

Prof. Nataliia Yehorchenkova, M.Sc., PhD, Dr.Sc, Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava

Feedback report

1	What aspects of the "Territorial and Project Management" course did you find most valuable or impactful?	a) Course content	8
		b) Instructor's teaching style	3
		c) Course activities	8
		d) Other (please specify):	1
2	How well did the course materials (e.g., readings, videos, assignments) align with your learning goals and expectations?	a) Aligned perfectly	7
		b) Mostly aligned	11
		c) Partially aligned	2
		d) Did not align	1
3	Were the concepts covered in the course presented in a clear and understandable manner?	a) Very clear and understandable	7
		b) Mostly clear and understandable	10
		c) Somewhat clear and understandable	4
		d) Not clear and understandable	
4	Did the course activities (e.g., discussions, group projects) enhance your understanding of project management principles?	a) Yes, significantly	8
		b) Yes, to some extent	10
		c) No, not really	2
		d) Did not participate in course activities	
5	What did you find most challenging about the course content or structure, and how did you overcome these challenges?	a) Time management	7
		b) Understanding complex concepts	8
		c) Balancing workload with other commitments	8
		d) Other (please specify): _____	1
6	Did the teachers provide sufficient support and guidance throughout the course? Please elaborate on your experience.	a) Yes, always	15
		b) Yes, most of the time	3
		c) No, occasionally	3
		d) No, rarely or never	
7	How would you rate the relevance of the course content to real-world applications in territorial and project management?	a) Highly relevant	10
		b) Moderately relevant	10
		c) Somewhat relevant	2
		d) Not relevant	
8	Were there any specific topics or areas you wish were covered in more depth or addressed differently?	a) Yes	7
		b) No	14
9		a) Manageable	15

	<p>How would you describe the overall pace and workload of the course? Was it manageable, too light, or too heavy?</p>	b) Too light	3
		c) Too heavy	3
10	<p>What suggestions do you have for improving the "Territorial and Project Management" course for future students?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More about financing projects from EU funds - I think this course shouldn't be over in a week. I think should be spread over two weeks. - That it should be prioritised the week of the course, and not happen at the same time with other courses or workshops – it can be difficult to follow because of its intensive nature. It would be best for the performance of the students (so they don't struggle with work overload or exhaustion). - I don't have any suggestions. The course was good and I am satisfied with everything. Thank you! - More discussions and activities during lessons. - To extend this course over more days. Because sometimes it was difficult to seat for 3 hours listening to lectures. And perhaps there were more days of preparation for the practical part. And everything was great. Thank you! - Consider not only Kanban but also Scrum in more detail. - More pictures in presentation. Good lecture and practical part. It was interesting and cognitively. - To make it two weeks - Maybe more oriented practical activity. I was feeling that there was no practical instructions or boundary. - Make more interactions with students. Thank you for teaching. - Split the course into two weeks because it was a little hard. 	

1. WHAT ASPECTS OF THE "TERRITORIAL AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT" COURSE DID YOU FIND MOST VALUABLE OR IMPACTFUL?

- a) Course content
- b) Instructor's teaching style
- c) Course activities
- d) Other (please specify):

2. HOW WELL DID THE COURSE MATERIALS (E.G., READINGS, VIDEOS, ASSIGNMENTS) ALIGN WITH YOUR LEARNING GOALS AND EXPECTATIONS?

- a) Aligned perfectly
- b) Mostly aligned
- c) Partially aligned
- d) Did not align

3. WERE THE CONCEPTS COVERED IN THE COURSE PRESENTED IN A CLEAR AND UNDERSTANDABLE MANNER?

- a) Very clear and understandable
- b) Mostly clear and understandable
- c) Somewhat clear and understandable
- d) Not clear and understandable

4. DID THE COURSE ACTIVITIES (E.G., DISCUSSIONS, GROUP PROJECTS) ENHANCE YOUR UNDERSTANDING OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT PRINCIPLES?

- a) Yes, significantly
- b) Yes, to some extent
- c) No, not really
- d) Did not participate in course activities

5. WHAT DID YOU FIND MOST CHALLENGING ABOUT THE COURSE CONTENT OR STRUCTURE, AND HOW DID YOU OVERCOME THESE CHALLENGES?

- a) Time management
- b) Understanding complex concepts
- c) Balancing workload with other commitments
- d) Other (please specify): _____

6. DID THE TEACHERS PROVIDE SUFFICIENT SUPPORT AND GUIDANCE THROUGHOUT THE COURSE? PLEASE ELABORATE ON YOUR EXPERIENCE.

- a) Yes, always
- b) Yes, most of the time
- c) No, occasionally
- d) No, rarely or never

7. HOW WOULD YOU RATE THE RELEVANCE OF THE COURSE CONTENT TO REAL-WORLD APPLICATIONS IN TERRITORIAL AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT?

■ a) Highly relevant ■ b) Moderately relevant ■ c) Somewhat relevant ■ d) Not relevant

8. WERE THERE ANY SPECIFIC TOPICS OR AREAS YOU WISH WERE COVERED IN MORE DEPTH OR ADDRESSED DIFFERENTLY?

■ a) Yes ■ b) No

9. HOW WOULD YOU DESCRIBE THE OVERALL PACE AND
WORKLOAD OF THE COURSE? WAS IT MANAGEABLE, TOO LIGHT,
OR TOO HEAVY?

■ a) Manageable ■ b) Too light ■ c) Too heavy

2. Module description

Intermediate piloted module was provided within the course I-RP-E-UI “Territorial and Project Management” from February, 12, 2025 to May, 16 2025. The format of the module was provided as intensive block-week that included 40 hours. The theme of the block week reflected current problems in the field of project and territory management. During the block week, both theoretical developments and their application in practice were considered.

Teachers:

- Prof. Oleksii Yehorchenkov, M.Sc., PhD, Dr.Sc, Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
- Prof. Nataliia Yehorchenkova, M.Sc., PhD, Dr.Sc, Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
- Prof.Olena Verenyh, , M.Sc., PhD, Dr.Sc, Project Management Department, Kyiv National University of Technology and Architecture, Kyiv, Ukraine

Отметка времени	Адрес электронной почты	1.What aspects of the "Territorial and Project Management" course did you find most valuable or impactful?	2.How well did the course materials (e.g., readings, videos, assignments) align with your learning goals and expectations?	3.Were the concepts covered in the course presented in a clear and understandable manner?	4.Did the course activities (e.g., discussions, group projects) enhance your understanding of project management principles?	5.What did you find most challenging about the course content or structure, and how did you overcome these challenges?	6. Did the teachers provide sufficient support and guidance throughout the course? Please elaborate on your experience.	7.How would you rate the relevance of the course content to real-world applications in territorial and project management?	8.Were there any specific topics or areas you wish were covered in more depth or addressed differently?	9.How would you describe the overall pace and workload of the course? Was it manageable, too light, or too heavy?	10. What suggestions do you have for improving the "Territorial and Project Management" course for future students?
6.1.2025 17:30:26	P.Rumyantseva_FIT_11_22_B_d@knute.edu.ua	Course content	Aligned perfectly	Very clear and understandable	Yes, significantly	Understanding complex concepts	Yes, always	Highly relevant	No	Manageable	

1. What aspects of the "Territorial and Project Management" course did you find most valuable or impactful?

1 ответ

2. How well did the course materials (e.g., readings, videos, assignments) align with your learning goals and expectations?

1 ответ

3. Were the concepts covered in the course presented in a clear and understandable manner?

1 ответ

4. Did the course activities (e.g., discussions, group projects) enhance your understanding of project management principles?

1 ответ

- Yes, significantly
- Yes, to some extent
- No, not really
- Did not participate in course activities

5. What did you find most challenging about the course content or structure, and how did you overcome these challenges?

1 ответ

- Time management
- Understanding complex concepts
- Balancing workload with other commitments

6. Did the teachers provide sufficient support and guidance throughout the course? Please elaborate on your experience.

1 ответ

- Yes, always
- Yes, most of the time
- No, occasionally
- No, rarely or never

7. How would you rate the relevance of the course content to real-world applications in territorial and project management?

1 ответ

- Highly relevant
- Moderately relevant
- Somewhat relevant
- Not relevant

8. Were there any specific topics or areas you wish were covered in more depth or addressed differently?

1 ответ

- Yes
- No

9. How would you describe the overall pace and workload of the course? Was it manageable, too light, or too heavy?

1 ответ

3. Module description

Intermediate piloted module was provided within the course International Lectures “Project management for EU urban transformation in the context of climate change and energy transition”, 2-5, June, 16 2025. The format of the lectures was provided as intensive block-week that included 40 hours. The theme of the block week reflected current problems in the field of project and territory management. During the block week, both theoretical developments and their application in practice were considered.

Teachers:

- prof. Marosh Finka, Ing.arch., PhD, Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
- Ing. Ľubomír Jamečný, PhD., Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
- Doc. Ing. Vladimír Ondrejčka, PhD., Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
- Doc. Ing. Milan Husar, PhD, Spatial Planning department, Institute of Management, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava

Отмет ка вре ме ни	Адрес электронной почты	Name	Instituti on / Organiz ation	Which lecture(s) did you attend?	How would you rate the overall quality of the lectur e(s)?	How relevant was the topic to your academic/prof essional interests?	How would you rate the speake r(s)?	How satisfied are you with the organizati on of the event (technical support, timing, communi cation, etc.)?	What did you like the most about the lecture(s) ?	What could be improv ed in future events?	Woul d you like to atte nd simil ar lectur es in the futur e?	Any additi onal comme nts or sugges tions?
18.06. 2025 10:25: 48	dos@management.su mdu.edu.ua	Denys Smolenn ikov	Sumy State Universi ty	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipal ities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipal ities for SMART Develop ment,	Good	Very relevant	Good	Satisfied	I have enjoyed the session "Managin g Changes in Energy Transition Projects". Presentati on materials were helpful.	Make more engage ment with listener s	Yes	

				Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful communication within EU projects								
18.06.2025 11:08:14	tetiana.morozova@ukr.net	Tetiana	NATIONAL TRANSPORT UNIVERSITY	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development, Managing changes in energy transition projects,	Excellent	Very relevant	Excellent	Very satisfied	clarity and professionalism		Yes	Good job!

				Setting up effective and impactful communication within EU projects								
18.06.2025 11:18:26	viktor.onyshchuk@knu.ua	Viktor Onyshchuk	Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development, Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful	Excellent	Very relevant	Excellent	Very satisfied	Clear and structured theory, relevant examples	Apply more real cases to theoretical approach	Yes	

				communi- cation within EU projects								
18.06. 2025 11:59: 37	menshov.o@ukr.net	Oleksan- dr Menshov	Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipal- ities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipal- ities for SMART Develop- ment, Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful communi- cation within EU projects	Excell- ent	Somewhat relevant	Excell- ent	Very satisfied	Interdisci- plinary studies	More specific case studies, data discuss- ion	Yes	Thank you for the invitati- on

18.06.2025 12:10:03	irynekostetska@ukr.net	Iryna Kostetska	National university of Ostrog Academy	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development, Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful communication within EU projects	Excellent	Very relevant	Excellent	Very satisfied				Yes
18.06.2025 12:44:26	a.yevdokymova@job.sumdu.edu.ua	Alona Yevdokymova	Sumy State University	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and	Excellent	Very relevant	Excellent	Very satisfied				Yes

				Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development								
18.06.2025 13:23:17	oshabatura@knu.ua	Oleksandr Shabatura	Taras Schevchenko National University of Kyiv	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury	Good	Somewhat relevant	Excellent	Very satisfied	teaching style, clear and understandable	It's difficult to say	Yes	thanks for the opportunity to participate in the event
18.06.2025 13:57:47	ellena06.84@ukr.net	Olena Sorochynska	National Transport University	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and	Excellent	Very relevant	Excellent	Very satisfied			Yes	

				Municipalities for SMART Development, Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful communication within EU projects								
18.06.2025 15:27:27	11spopov@gmail.com	Stanislav	National Transport University	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development,	Good	Very relevant	Good	Very satisfied	Examples of Practical cases	Some elements of workshops, timing.	Yes	Thank you for the invitation. It was a great opportunity to connect with the European community and to receive a certificate,

				Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful communication within EU projects									which is very important to me.
18.06.2025 15:53:05	demidov@knu.ua	Vsevolod Demydov	TSNU of Kyiv	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development, Managing changes in energy transition projects,	Excellent	Somewhat relevant	Excellent	Very satisfied	Practical experience of speakers	Include practical cases	Yes		

				Setting up effective and impactful communication within EU projects								
18.06.2025 19:33:10	irarevak@gmail.com	Iryna	Lviv State University of Internal Affairs	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development, Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful	Good	Somewhat relevant	Good	Satisfied			Yes	

				communi- cation within EU projects								
19.06. 2025 10:29: 17	y.artemchuk@ntu.edu. ua	Yuliia	-	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipal ities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipal ities for SMART Develop- ment, Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful communi- cation within EU projects	Excell- ent	Somewhat relevant	Good	Satisfied	~	Yes	Yes	-

19.06.2025 11:12:06	o.kosharnyi@gmail.com	Oleksandr	National transport university	Smart Future of Regions, Cities, and Municipalities – or Smart Is Not a Luxury, Strategic Planning of Cities and Municipalities for SMART Development, Managing changes in energy transition projects, Setting up effective and impactful communication within EU projects	Excellent	Somewhat relevant	Excellent	Satisfied	Oil	Offline	Yes	Offline
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Institution / Organization

Копировать

13 ответов

Which lecture(s) did you attend?

Копировать

13 ответов

How would you rate the overall quality of the lecture(s)?

 Копировать

13 ответов

How relevant was the topic to your academic/professional interests?

 Копировать

13 ответов

How would you rate the speaker(s)?

 Копировать

13 ответов

How satisfied are you with the organization of the event
(technical support, timing, communication, etc.)?

 Копировать

13 ответов

What did you like the most about the lecture(s)?

9 ответов

clarity and professionalism

I have enjoyed the session "Managing Changes in Energy Transition Projects".
Presentation materials were helpful.

teaching style, clear and understandable

Practical experience of speakers

Clear and structured theory, relevant examples

Oil

~

Interdisciplinary studies

Examples of Practical cases

What could be improved in future events?

9 ответов

-
- Make more engagement with listeners
- It's difficult to say
- Include practical cases
- Apply more real cases to theoretical approach
- Offline
- Yes
- More specific case studies, data discussion
- Some elements of workshops, timing.

Would you like to attend similar lectures in the future?

 Копировать

13 ответов

Any additional comments or suggestions?

6 ответов

- Good job!
- thanks for the opportunity to participate in the event
- Offline
-
- Thank you for the invitation
- Thank you for the invitation. It was a great opportunity to connect with the European community and to receive a certificate, which is very important to me.